

Sustainable Water Quality Monitoring with Energy-Efficient Wireless Sensor Networks

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Abstract: *This paper propose a more efficient water monitoring and control system for water utility to reduce the current water wastage problem. This approach will help utilities operators improve low cost water management systems, specially by using rising technologies and IoT is one of them. The Internet of Things (IoT) could prove to be one of the most important methods for developing more utility-proper systems and for making the consumption of water resources more efficient.*

Keywords: *Water Monitoring , Water resources, Node MCU , Internet of Things*

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently drinking water is very prized for all the humans. In recent times all the humans and creatures on the earth all the human beings and creatures on the earth facing troubles because of growing population, aging infrastructure etc. So its too important to find the solution for water monitoring & control system .For that IoT is blessing as a solution. Microcontrollers and sensors are very useful for creating that system. Ultrasonic Sensor is used to measuring water level. The other parameters like pH, TDS, and Turbidity of the water should be calculated. The calculated values from the sensors can be processed by the Microcontrollers and uploaded to the internet through the Wi-Fi module (ESP 8266). Analysis can also be done on sensed data to pick out for the solutions. In design various controller like Arduino Uno, Raspberry PI b+ are used as a core controller. The invented system is used some IoT modules for accessing sensor data from the core controller to the cloud. The data which is obtain from the sensors can be shown on the internet and provides facilities for screening the data on mobile phones or web application.

II. RELATED WORK

This study discusses the design and current development of system having low cost to monitor real time values and also to control the system using IoT. To measure the various parameters of the water, array of sensors are included in the system. The parameters which can be measured are like temperature, PH, turbidity of the water. Core controller can process the value measured from the sensors. The Arduino Uno model can be used to control the system. Lastly, to access the sensor data on internet, cloud computing can be used.

Daigavane et al. (2016) designed water Quality Monitoring System Based on IOT in Advances in Wireless and Mobile Communications, Research India Publications for Monitoring of Turbidity, PH & Temperature of Water makes use of water detection sensor with unique advantage and existing GSM network. The system can monitor water quality automatically, and it is low in cost and does not require people on duty. So the water quality testing is likely to be more economical, convenient and fast. The system has good flexibility. Only by replacing the corresponding sensors and changing the relevant software programs, this system can be used to monitor other water quality parameters. The operation is simple. Energy management decision is made dynamically at runtime, as the optimum for long-term traffic statistics under the constraint of the service delay. By keeping the embedded devices in the environment for monitoring enables self protection (i.e., smart environment) to the environment. To implement this need to deploy the sensor devices in the environment for collecting the data and analysis. By deploying sensor devices in the environment, we can bring the environment into real life i.e. it can interact with other objects through the network. Then the collected data and analysis results will be available to the end user through the Wi-Fi.

Deepalakshmi et al (2018), designed Real Time Water Contamination Monitoring System using IoT to avoid Water borne diseases in Textile Cluster Areas focused on the critical evaluation on the role and reliability of the lake monitoring system in Textile Cluster Areas. Primary and secondary resources were used in the project execution. For the primary data, a survey has been conducted in the areas of Tamil nadu. Secondary resources derived from various publications including books and journals were integrated to support the findings. Based on the results of the various test cases, system functionalities were validated. It consumes low power, and it is a small size, where the size is a good use for a crucial point-of-sale technology criterion. Among four sensors, only two of the sensors collect the data in the form of analog signals.

Ashwini et al. In 2019 designed Real Time Water Contamination Monitoring System using IoT to avoid Water borne diseases in Textile Cluster Areas presents the economical solution to avoid contamination of water in residential overhead tanks. The proposed system consists of multi sensors connected to NodeMCU to collect the water parameters achieved using machine learning algorithms. And the alert message is sent with a delay to the user before the water gets contaminated. The system helps to save the water from contamination and is also cost effective. The future scope for this is to detect the diseases caused by different parameters and finding the appropriate solution for to clean the tank. Also biosensors can be used to detect the microbacterias for better quality of water

Joshi et al. (2020), designed Node MCU and Blynk aided Advanced Water Quality Monitoring Set-up proposed with the advanced technique of Water Quality Monitoring. This intended approach helped to replace the former way of manual testing by updating the sensors information over an application's platform. Here, we measured the various chemical parameters of water like pH and total dissolved solids as well as physical parameters of water like turbidity and temperature to monitor the supplied water quality.. The data collected and examined through this way took a large amount of time and thus the changing technology demanded a new technique to overcome all such limitations and make this task a user-friendly one. Therefore, the proposed method worked to erase out all such lacunas with help of new emerging technology of machine-user relationship wherein the data updated over any setup could be communicated to a human being at his fingertips. This technique helped an individual to keep track of minute variations that happened in parameters of supplied water with time. The latest parameter's data was hosted on Blynk application with help of ESP8266 an in-built Wifi-module in NodeMCU. The advanced setup including NodeMCU, Blynk and various meters proved to be the time and effort-saving method which could definitely take place of the traditional way of analyzing the water quality.

Varman et al. in (2020), designed IoT based Water Quality Monitoring and Flow Control of Tank Water suitable implementation model that consists of different sensors and other modules, their functional architecture is shown in figure. In this implemented functional model, the author proposed Arduino UNO (R3) with ESP8266 module for wireless connectivity. Inbuilt ADC and ESP8266 module connect the embedded device to internet. Sensors are connected to Arduino UNO board for monitoring, ADC will transform the sensor reading to its digital value and from that value the corresponding water parameters (pH,NTU) and other parameters (level, flow and object detection) will be validated. After sensing the data from different sensors, which are placed in particular area of interest, the sensed data will be automatically sent to the user via MQTT, when a proper connection is established with server node.

Rahman et al. in year 2020 designed Internet of Things (IoT) Based Water Quality Monitoring System implementing the system on some water resources, the author achieved data and their suitability. In this the author tested four water samples. Those are water from purifier source, water from pond, water mixed with lemon and water mixed with calcium hydroxides. If the pH value is above basic (means higher than 7.5) water is alkane. If it is below 6.5 the water is acidic.

Rakshitha et al. (2020), designed A Review on Water Level & Quality Monitoring System important aspect in many applications such as chemical industries, household, pharmaceutical industries, nuclear power generation plants etc.. The proposed methodology can be used in saving man power and electricity.

Pasika et al. In year 2020 Smart water quality monitoring system with cost-effective using IoT proposed in this paper is an efficient, inexpensive IoT solution for real-time water quality monitoring. The developed system having Arduino Mega and NodeMCU target boards are interfaced with several sensors successfully. An efficient algorithm is developed in real-time, to track water quality. The measured pH value ranges from 6.5 to 7.5 for Hyderabad Metropolitan city supply water and 7 to 8.5 for groundwater. The measured value of turbidity ranges from 600 to 2000 NTU for both Hyderabad Metropolitan city supply water and groundwater. A web-based application i.e., ThingSpeak is used to monitor the parameters such as pH value, the turbidity of the water, level of water in the tank, temperature and humidity of the surrounding atmosphere through the webserver. Further, these measured parameters also monitored in ThingSpeak mobile application. Also, this work needs to be carried out to analyse several other parameters like electrical conductivity, free residual chlorine, nitrates, but dissolved oxygen in the water cannot be monitored properly.

III. RELATION WITH IOT

In past, the living of individuals has been changed due to the Internet. The IoT has been became an emerging research area because of need of an establishment for connecting things, sensors and other smart technologies [13]. IoT is known as internet’s advanced version. Information related to physical objects can be immediately accessed by IoT and results into novel system having high efficiency and outputs. In IoT, a number of main technologies are there like ubiquitous computing, RFIP, wireless sensor network, cloud computing[13].Cloud computing, a large-scale, low cost processing unit and also an IP based connection mostly used for calculation and storage purpose. The water quality monitoring application contains many distributed monitoring sensors’ array and a wide distribution network. Separate monitoring system is also required in it as told in paper [13].This paper introduces cloud computing techniques for screening values on the internet.

❖ Hardware Availability:-

Methodology:-

To design the proposed water quality monitoring system for the current research work, the sensors to be used and the system design is discussed in this section.

Activity 1

Selection of Sensors & Development of microcontroller interface circuitry

The availability, affordability, and compatibility with microcontroller-based architecture will be the main reason for the selection of particular brand of water quality sensors. For the current work Atlas brand sensors can be used.

Atlas Scientific is an American company that has years of experience manufacturing high-performance water quality sensors which are widely used in scientific projects.

Temperature, pH, and DO sensors (electrodes) are connected to the microcontroller using their respective interface circuits.

a. Node MCU

Node MCU is an Open-source, Interactive, Programmable, Low cost, Simple, Smart, WI-FI enabled. It Contains firmware which runs on the ESP 8266 Wi-Fi SoC from Espressif Systems .

Fig:3 Node MCU^[15]

IV. PRESENT WATER MONITORING SYSTEM

This system will be built using Arduino Uno and Node MCU. Arduino Uno is connected with Water level sensor(HCSRO4), Turbidity Sensor, pH sensor, Wi-Fi module (ESP8266) that process and transfer sensed data to cloud. . And other side ultrasonic sensor connected with Node MCU. This stored data is accessed by users. This enables the user to check the level of water and if it goes full then automatic stop. Other parameters related to water like water quality can also monitored for prevent wastage of water

Fig: 4 Model Diagram

➤ WHY THIS PROJECT IS COST EFFECTIVE AND ENERGY EFFICIENT?

This paper will be definitely cost effective but after a long time. Because at same time ph, turbidity and water level are measured in this system. Only one system is so costly nowadays like RO water plant, which its cost is around 8 to 10 thousand and for water level, the water sensor also is costly around 2 to 4 thousand. So total cost

is around 12 to 15 thousand so this system is better than all things. Water is also saved. Water wastage problem also prevented. Electricity bill also being low.

A comparison of Arduino, Raspberry Pi and ESP8266 Node MCU

Table 1: A comparison of development boards

	<u>Arduino</u>	<u>Raspberry Pi</u>	<u>ESP8266 Node MCU</u>
Developer	Arduino	Raspberry Pi Foundation	ESP8266 open source community
Type	Single board microcontroller	Mini computer	Single board microcontroller
Operating System	None	Linux	XTOS
CPU	Atmel, ARM, Intel	ARM Cortex	LXT106
Clock Speed	16 MHz	1.2GHz	26 MHz – 52 MHz
Memory	32KB	1-4GB	Upto 128MB
Storage	1KB	MicroSDHC Slot	4MB
Power	USB, Battery, Power Supply	USB, Power Supply	USB
Operating Voltage	5V	5V	3.3V
I/O Connectivity	SPI I2C UART GPIO	SPI DSI UART SdioCSI GPIO	UART, GPIO

Arduino and Raspberry Pi do not have built-in support for wireless networks. Developers will have to add a wifi or cellular module to the board and write code to access the wireless module. So open source IoT development board called NodeMCU is used and allows you to code your device using Lua scripts. One of its most unique features is that it has built-in support for wifi connectivity. It is a very inexpensive System-on-a-Chip (SoC) called the ESP8266. The ESP8266, designed and manufactured by Espressif Systems, contains all crucial elements of the modern computer: CPU, RAM, networking (wifi), and even a modern operating system and SDK. This makes NodeMCU a smart choice to play with the IoT.

Performance: This module provides simple performance measurement for an application. It samples the program counter roughly every 50 microseconds and builds a histogram of the values that it finds. Since there is only a small amount of memory to store the histogram, the user can specify which area of code is of interest. The default is the entire flash which contains code. Once the hotspots are identified, then the run can then be repeated with different areas and at different resolutions to get as much information as required.

SOFTWARE MODULE DEVELOPMENT:-

➤ HOW TO USE CLOUD?

- This system is using WI-Fi module (Esp8266) to send the sensor data to the cloud.
- All the sensors are connected with Wi-Fi module. Wi-Fi module needs the internet.
- So here Mobile data or Wi-Fi is the access point for the internet. And after all this data sends to the cloud (Thingspeak).

➤ RESULTS (DATA STORED ON THE CLOUD)

Fig:5 Result of Ultrasonic Sensor on Thingspeak Cloud (Wi-Fi Module)

Fig:6 Result of Ultrasonic Sensor on Thingspeak (Node MCU)Cloud

Fig:7 Result of pH Sensor on Thingspeak Cloud

Fig:8 Result of Turbidity Sensor on Thingspeak Cloud

Here, All the sensors like pH, Turbidity & Ultrasonic sensor are connected with different microcontrollers like Arduino Uno & Node MCU. And three sensors pH, turbidity, Ultrasonic sensor are connected with Arduino Uno & ESP 8266 to sending data to the cloud. One ultrasonic sensor is connected with the Node MCU. In 2nd figure Node MCU is connected with an ultrasonic sensor. The water level is shown in inches (in) and centimeters (cm). The graph is plotted by using sensor data. This sensor data are sent to the cloud (Thingspeak) using Node MCU & Wi-Fi module.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper is presented the design and development of IoT based water monitoring & control system. For this some sensors are used. The collected data from all the sensors are used for analysis purpose for better solution of water problems. The data is sent to the cloud server via Wi-Fi module ESP8266. So this application will be the best challenger in real time monitoring & control system and use to solve all the water related problems.

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